

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B279
Date: 10 March 2007
Take Off 08:00:56Z
Landing: 14:10:44Z
Flight Time 6h09m48

Campaign: GFDEX – Targeted Observations

Operating Area: South of Iceland

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Steve Ball	FAAM
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	G. Nina Petersen	University of Toronto
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
7	AVAPS / CCM2	Stuart Heath	FAAM
8	Mission Scientist 2	Jon Egill Kristjansson	University of Oslo
9	Mission Scientist 3	Carling Hay	University of Toronto
10	Mission Scientist 4	Emma Irvine	University of Reading
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Flight Track:

B279 Track 10-MAR-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b279

Date: 10 Mar 2007

Project: GFDEX Targeted Observations and Breaking Wave

Location: South of Iceland

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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073413		Start-Up	0.64 kft	290	63 58.45 N, 22 35.80W
073413		INU	0.64 kft	290	To Nav
080056		T/O	2.0 kft	249	Keflavik
081032		Video	18.9 kft	234	Start FFC & DFC
090401	090558	Profile 1	24.0 - 26.0 kft	216	
090559	105943	Run 1.1	26.0 kft	214	
090653		Sonde	26.1 kft	209	Launch #01
092842		Sonde	26.0 kft	198	Launch #02
094236		Videos	26.0 kft	197	Change Tapes
095052		Sonde	26.0 kft	201	Launch #03
101022		Sonde	26.0 kft	205	Launch #04
103103		Sonde	26.0 kft	175	Launch #05
105306		Sonde	26.1 kft	176	Launch #06
105943	110205	Profile 2	26.0 - 27.0 kft	353	
110205	125708	Run 2.1	27.1 - 27.0 kft	004	
110805		Sonde	27.0 kft	028	Launch #07
111449		Video	27.0 kft	031	Change Tapes
111901		Sonde	27.0 kft	033	Launch #08
112945		Sonde	27.0 kft	038	Launch #09
113958		Sonde	27.0 kft	041	Launch #10
115023		Sonde	27.0 kft	042	Launch #11
120120		Sonde	27.0 kft	041	Launch #12
124709		Video	27.0 kft	046	Change Tapes
125217		Sonde	27.0 kft	055	Launch #13
125647		Sonde	27.0 kft	064	Launch #14, failed
125709	125852	Profile 3	27.0 - 25.2 kft	065	Abort & climb
130626		Sonde	27.0 kft	250	Launch #15
131113		Descent	21.3 kft	061	10 degrees bank
131708	135300	Run 3	15.0 - 13.8 kft	242	
141044		Land	0.74 kft	090	Keflavik
141734		Shutdown	0.79 kft	180	63'58.43N, 22'35.78W

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B279 Track 10-MAR-07

GFDex Sortie Brief – B279 - 10 March 2007
Targeted observations and a breaking wave

Mission Scientist 1 – G. Nina Petersen

Mission Scientists – Jon Egill Kristjansson, Emma Irvine, Carling Hay

Aims

- Sensitive area targeting in an ETKF sensitive area
- Mapping the 3-D structure downstream and upstream of a baroclinic cyclone moving northeastward
- Measuring the vertical structure of a breaking wave over Hvannadalshnjukur

GFD13	Time	Manoeuvre	Distance (nm)	Duration (min)	Total time (min)
1	08.00	Take off Keflavík transit to 60°48N 30W.	281		
2		Straight level run at 25-30kft from 60°48N 30W to 56°42N 34°30W. 4 dropsonde releases, every ~94 nm.	283		
3		Straight level run at 25-30kft from 56°42N 34° 30W to 53°30N 33°W. 1 dropsonde release at midpoint.	199		
4		Straight level run at 25-30kft from 53°30N 33W to 60°N 26W. 7 dropsonde releases, every ~75 nm.	452		
5		Straight level run at 25-30kft from 60°N 26°W to 63°48N 17°50W. Drop a sonde here.	324		
6		Straight level run at 25-30kft from 63°48N to 17°50W to 64°07N 16°09W. Drop 1 sonde at 64°N 16°50W.	50		
7		Descent to 15kft and run the same leg back to 63°48N to 17°50W.	50		
8		Transit to Keflavik. Total distance 1765nm	126		

Mission Scientists Debriefing Sheet

Flight No. 279

Date: 10.03.2007

Sortie Objectives: Sensitive area targeting in an ETKF MOGREPS sensitive area. Mapping out the 3-D structure of on the warm and cold side of a baroclinic cyclone. Measuring the vertical structure of a breaking wave over Hvannadalshnjúkur, Iceland's highest mountain.

Summary of weather: The cyclone was predicted to be located 57°N 33°W at 12Z. In the vicinity of Iceland the winds were light but the warm front had advanced by at least a degree northward from the satellite image at 0511Z. Strong flight level winds from the south-southwest.

Flight pattern: Transit from Keflavik to 60°48N 30°W. Four dropsondes from 60°48N 30°W to 56°42N 34°30W. The first two measured southeasterly winds at 500hPa, 50kt and 80kt respectively, with east 25 and then 50kt at 925hPa. The third one measured southerly winds at both levels, 35kt at low levels and 50kt at 500hPa, indicating that the cyclone might be farther west than predicted. The last dropsonde of the leg is thought to have ascended into the centre of the cyclone, light winds at all levels and a surface pressure of 948hPa. This is lower pressure than predicted by any model. The rest of the dropsondes measured south or south-southwesterly 50-85kt at low levels but 60-100kt at 500hPa. Maximum wind speed at flight level was found east of the cyclone centre, 74 m/s. The cloud cover was broken in the vicinity of the cyclone centre, but dense cirrus in the warm front. In the cold front the cloud tops were at about 27kft. The ozone peaked in the surrounding of the cyclone centre, in both southerly and northerly dropsonde leg, at about 350ppb. Two dropsondes launched over Iceland. The second one failed so another one was released. One leg at 15kft underneath the Icelandic dropsonde leg.

Assessment of the Flight: Successful and interesting flight. The fact that the cyclone was located differently than predicted makes this an interesting case to simulate and an interesting SAP case. All the dropsonde observations got into the GTS on time. The dropsonde releases over Iceland showed not as much wave activity as anticipated. Two possible explanations: The dropsonde over Hvannadalshnjúkur came down on the top of the mountain, not in the lee. The wave was not at its strongest at 1300 when the dropsondes were launched and dissipating. Longest science flight of the aircraft, 6h 9m 48s, distance ~1850nm.

Problems: One dropsonde without launch line. Another one released.

Guðrún Nína Petersen

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B27A**... Date **10.03.07** Name **GNP**..... Page **1** of **2**.

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
08.00					Take off
08.06		24kft.			O ₂ jumped up to ~100ppb for 3 min while climbing.
09.04	P1				Cirrus started bet. 62N. climb to 26kft. 12mm drizzle
09.06.53	2260	26kft			DS1
09.16		26kft			light turb.
09.22					coming out of cirrus.
—					dense clouds below strato cum? icy in tops drizzle 30?
09.28.42		26kft			DS2
09.35					↑ O ₂ again 2 peaks. drizzle 20mm
09.50.52					DS3
09.49		26kft.			O ₂ 290 ppb 300ppb at 09.50 +350 at 09.55
10.10					DS4 cirrus
10.31.03		26kft.			DS5
10.35					O ₂ down to ~200 ppb
10.53.06					DS6
					max flight level wind ~ 9.30 62m/s lowest 10.06 23
11.01		27kft			O ₂ up to 300 ppb
11.08.05		27kft			DS7 convection a lte cum? more to east than west strato cum?
11.19.01		27kft.			DS8
11.15		27kft.			O ₂ 300 ppb 11.18: O ₂ down to 300
11.29.45					DS9 220 11.25

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B279**... Date **10.03.07**... Name **GNP**... Page **2** of **2**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11.39.58		27kft			DS 10
11.31					ozone ↓ to 150 ppb 11.31
—					100 ppb 11.39.
11.50.23		27kft.			DS 11
11.52					Clouds 27kft. cold front
—					light turb w icy thinness cloud tops via
12.01.20					DS 12
11.58					ozone ↓ 50 ppb
					max flight level winds 11.35 74kts
12.52.17.					DS 13, Ho's ⁶³⁴⁹ 17549
12.56.47					DS 14 No launch!!
					prof. down to 15kft.
13.06.26					DS 15
13.07					desc. to 15kft.
					Θ ~ by 0.25 deg. not more
					very light turb.
					at 13.15 Θ ~ 306.5 K
					at 13.25 Θ ~ 310.5 K
14.11					LAND 6h09min
					~ 1850 nm.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B279

Date: 10/03/07

Operator: KFT

Page 1 of 1

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
08:06			Bases incr'd								PCASP Vref=7V, Heaters ON
08:14:00	46	0.06	2	-	1.5	100	11	Switched off			FL240 – 2DP noisy
08:17			Bases incr'd								
08:20:00	75	0.06	4	-	47	250	11,8	-	-		
08:25:00	28	0.13	7	-	49	175	11,8	-	-		PCASP Vref=6.5V
08:28			Bases incr'd								
08:30:00	91	0.07	18	-	143	575	8,11	-	-		
08:35:00	102	0.31	43	-	172	326	8	-	-		
08:40:00	25	0.21	67	-	112	400	8	-	-		
08:50:00	28	0.38	147	-	178	700	8,3	-	-		
08:55:00	153	0.23	188	-	77	575	8,3	-	-		
09:00:00	185	0.27	239	-	128	625	83	-	-		
09:05:00	275	0.30	317	-	346	625	8,3	-	-		FL250
09:06:54	41	0.38	329	-	530	375	8	-	-		SONDE 1 FL260
09:14			Bases incr'd								
09:15:00	3173	0.08	404	-	200	600	8	-	-		
09:20:00	40	0.09	494	-	28	250	8	-	-		
09:25:00	31	0.06	496	-	0	0		-	-		
09:28:43	37	0.06	496	-	0	0		-	-		SONDE 2
09:40:00	41	0.07	496	-	0	0		-	-		
09:45:00	76	0.06	496	-	0	0		-	-		
09:50:54	81	0.06	496	-	0	0		-	-		SONDE 3; CIP RESTARTED
10:10:24	88	0.06	497	-	NOISE			-	-		SONDE 4
10:31:05	90	0.07	498	-	0	0		-	-		SONDE 5
10:53:08	126	0.06	499	-	0	0		-	-		SONDE 6
11:02:13	174	0.06	499	-	0	0		-	-		FL270
11:08:06	101	0.06	499	-	0	0		-	-		SONDE 7
11:19:04	168	0.06	499	-	0	0		-	-		SONDE 8
11:29:46	164	0.06	499	-	0	0		-	-		SONDE 9
11:39:59	115	0.06	500	-	0	0		-	-		SONDE 10
11:50:25	172	0.06	500	-	0	0		-	-		SONDE 11
11:53:30	245	0.06	501	-	189	275	8,11	-	-		FFSSP BASES INCREASED
12:00:00	253	0.18	530	-	500	475	8,11	-	-		
12:01:23	213	0.07	536	-	118	175	8,11	-	-		SONDE 12

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B279

Date: 10/03/07

Operator: KFT

Page 2 of 2

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
12:05:00	234	0.07	564	-	416	350	8,4	-	-		FFSSP BASES INCREASED
12:10:00	185	0.06	586	-	29	200	11,4,9	-	-		
12:15:00	316	0.13	633	-	610	625	9,4	-	-		
12:20:00	256	0.12	691	-	176	700	9,4	-	-		
12:30:00	199	0.06	721	-	8	300	8,11	-	-		
12:36:00	360	0.08	754	-	83	650	9,4,8	-	-		
12:40:00	190	0.08	782	-	172	325	8,11	-	-		
12:45:00	235	0.06	808	-	110	150	11,8	-	-		
12:50:00	217	0.06	816	-	99	175	11,8	-	-		
12:52:18	225	0.06	821	-	86	275	11,8	-	-		SONDE 13
12:55:00	278	0.11	828	-	172	225	11,8	-	-		
12:56:49	188	0.06	831	-	144	300	11,8	-	-		SONDE 14 FL270
12:58:14	238	0.07	833	-	86	250	8	-	-		FL260
13:00:00	279	0.09	837	-	135	300	8,11	-	-		FL270
13:05:00	221	0.07	848	-	121	200	8,11	-	-		
13:06:28	238	0.06	851	-	71	125	11	-	-		SONDE 15
13:07:30	234	0.08	853	-	165	200	11	-	-		FL260
13:08:10	266	0.11	854	-	150	275	8,11	-	-		FL250
13:08:54	232	0.08	857	-	85	325	8	-	-		FL240
13:09:36	297	0.06	859	-	55	250	8	-	-		FL230
13:10:27	269	0.07	861	-	48	425	8	-	-		FL220
13:11:24	225	0.06	863	-	52	550	8	-	-		FL210
13:12:21	276	0.06	865	-	24.5	250	8	-	-		FL200
13:13:09	266	0.06	865	-	0	0		-	-		FL190
13:14:07	276	0.06	866	-	0	0		-	-		FL180
13:15:04	353	0.06	973	-	0	0		-	-		FL170
13:16:05	365	0.07	1483	-	0	0		-	-		FL160 FFSSP FROZEN
13:17:08	249	0.06	0	-	0	0		-	-		FL150 FFSSP BASES INCR'D
13:20:00	151	0.06	0	-	0	0		-	-		
13:25:00	114	0.06	0	-	0	0		-	-		
13:30:00	47	0.06	2	-	41	600	8,4	-	-		
13:40:00	32	0.08	70	-	63	700	4,3,8	-	-		
13:45:00	32	0.11	108	-	45	525	4,8	-	-		2DP still noisy
13:50:00	34	0.37	153	-	55	650	4,8,3	-	-		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B279 **T/O:** 08:00:56
Date of flight: 10/03/07 **Land:** 14:10:44

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		To Exeter
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B279
Date of Flight: 10/03/07

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	66414 blocks
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Y	Size of Bnnn.dat = 397997
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 75858 Blocks written = 75858 Bad reads = 0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	Y	Start = 080000 End = 141500 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Are they non-zero in size?
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	Y	2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images No 2DP images. Switched off for much of flight since too high/cold for it to work. Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 08:00:00 End = 14:12:00 FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	Y	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X = A</p> <p>Start = 080000 End = 141500</p> <p>Time data processed to = 141128 2dproc files present? Y *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	Y	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored. Records = 23115, 178</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	Y	<p>X = A Y = (X+1) = B</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	Y	<p>Correlated? Y</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B279
Date of Flight: 10/03/07

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	Min size = 1 Vol flow rate = 1.15 080000 141000
3) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = B Y = X+1 = C
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	Y	Merged OK? Y

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B279	Date	10/03/2007
Page No.	1 of 2	Operator	SWH

GMT	Sonde No.	Event	Comments
		<i>e.g. launch, splashdown</i>	<i>e.g. windata? PTH data? Lat/Long</i>
090654	1	Launch	359.00 -39.60 82.00 185.40 45.90 -14.10 -29.998800 60.798000 7941.50 0
091616	1	Land	984.38 2.34 79.79 78.09 15.01 -11.45 -30.090325 60.889031 399.01 8
092842	2	Launch	359.20 -39.70 29.30 166.30 52.40 -15.30 -31.638900 59.435300 7937.90 0
093800	2	Land	969.33 1.45 98.32 76.91 22.32 -11.96 -31.842087 59.573882 483.89 6
095054	3	Launch	359.60 -36.60 6.87 169.60 34.60 -14.80 -33.126100 58.073700 7930.90 0
095934	3	Land	960.62 3.06 79.16 146.87 17.09 -12.77 -33.201805 58.189983 687.55 8
101024	4	Launch	359.40 -36.40 5.55 200.00 23.80 -14.10 -34.498400 56.697200 7933.30 0
101908	4	Land	948.15 3.35 84.57 142.84 8.03 -11.73 -34.504599 56.731596 99999.00 8
103106	5	Launch	359.40 -37.30 5.92 219.80 43.50 -14.00 -33.765100 55.099000 7934.70 0
104003	5	Land	954.18 3.09 93.07 221.76 30.90 -12.61 -33.550537 55.201867 741.66 7
105309	6	Launch	359.10 -41.40 7.42 209.10 47.20 -13.80 -32.998100 53.497300 7939.20 0
110222	6	Land	981.88 2.06 75.68 240.03 30.03 -11.29 -32.759047 53.585993 648.05 8
110806	7	Launch	344.30 -39.50 6.68 203.50 49.60 -16.40 -31.938100 54.649500 8230.00 0
111709	7	Land	971.99 2.21 88.57 208.18 35.49 -11.25 -31.695483 54.803234 658.45 6
111903	8	Launch	343.90 -36.90 5.54 197.30 51.80 -15.90 -30.882200 55.743500 8238.10 0
112824	8	Land	967.36 3.25 82.68 199.19 33.73 -12.07 -30.704330 55.958482 642.55 7
112948	9	Launch	344.00 -38.60 6.76 190.50 67.60 -15.60 -29.764000 56.827100 8236.50 0
113849	9	Land	967.16 3.81 59.89 182.11 34.99 -12.63 -29.677495 57.067103 612.98 8
114000	10	Launch	343.90 -39.60 10.21 187.60 72.80 -15.30 -28.582700 57.897600 8236.90 0
114911	10	Land	972.66 5.23 58.11 180.04 27.40 -13.11 -28.552970 58.159269 502.21 9
115024	11	Launch	344.00 -41.50 22.02 184.20 62.60 -14.00 -27.333000 58.953700 8234.80 0
120001	11	Land	975.36 6.97 62.57 187.37 24.04 -10.83 -27.309948 59.205445 419.72 6
120124	12	Launch	344.00 -42.00 75.64 187.40 51.50 -14.50 -25.993000 60.005100 8236.70 0
121101	12	Land	976.51 9.29 90.62 167.13 15.73 -11.80 -25.954442 60.190165 352.95 9
125218	13	Launch	344.10 -42.50 73.90 242.70 35.30 -13.40 -17.822600 63.801200 8234.20 0
130156	13	Land	995.42 2.61 63.67 59.74 2.45 -11.20 -17.644905 63.845265 306.59 6

125651	14	Launch	345.13	-17.28	4.45	243.57	81.16	-0.00
			-16.798607	64.007111	8782.31	5		
130122	14	Land	808.74	-7.00	52.37	66.17	1.03	-12.03
			-16.678893	64.025540	2021.33	7		
130627	15	Launch	344.00	-42.60	73.88	251.20	47.30	-13.50
			-16.841100	63.993900	8235.80	0		
131332	15	Land	774.75	-8.28	27.12	120.46	2.70	-12.83
			-16.650329	64.025351	2289.37	8		

Flight:

B279

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 15/03/2007
12:15:17

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

10/03/2007 17:16:21

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B279

Date: 010 March 2007

Instruments

1. Rosemount Temperatures – Almost 2°C difference between DeIced and NonDeIced temperatures. Replace elements for calibrated ones on return to Cranfield.
2. Sonde – No #14 failed, no launch detect.

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 10/3/07

Flight No: B274

Pre-Flighter: AMJ

<u>Item</u>	<u>√ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
		<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>		
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	To Review Coop GPS
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	WITH RADAR SET UP		
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
External Checks overleaf				→

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>Item</u>	<u>✓ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External</u>				
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				<u>Signed</u>
43	<input type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
44	<input type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Traps empty (weekly only)		
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HEATERS checked		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B279:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	Pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	21 Mar 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

4 x For/Rearward Facing Cameras
4 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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